

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Tawfiq**FIRST NAME:** Pawan Tatar**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1. What is the purpose of a research question in a qualitative dissertation?

To drive the study's goals and provide data analysis.¹

To establish methodological tools for data collection.

To structure the dissertation's organization.

To evaluate prior research in the field.

2. What is the purpose of an abstract in an academic dissertation?

A comprehensive description of the research methodology.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 220.

- It summarizes the whole dissertation.²**
 - Literature review.
 - It assesses the theoretical contributions of the dissertation.
3. Which citation style is the Turabian manual principally oriented toward?
- MLA and APA.
 - Harvard Referencing Style.
 - Vancouver Citation Style.
 - Chicago Notes and Bibliography.³**
4. What is a critical aspect of avoiding plagiarism in academic writing?
- Avoiding direct quotations.
 - Paraphrasing and citing all sources appropriately.⁴**
 - Passive voice in citing.
 - Cite without in-text references but have a bibliography.
5. Why is reliability important in qualitative research?

² James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University Press, 2017), 26.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 80–100.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

- Consistency of results under the same circumstances.**⁵
- Statistical approaches for quantification.
 - Making theoretical framework clear.
 - Relying only on statistical analysis.
6. What number of advice does the European Commission Style Guide give?
- Just as in recent years, Roman numerals should be used for dates and amounts.
 - Maintain consistency in formatting numbers and ranges.**⁶
 - Numbers under 10 should always be spelled out.
 - American rules for in text numbering.
7. What is a dissertation prospectus in the first place?
- In a summary of the research results.
 - Explicitly define the theoretical framework.
 - To propose the research design for approval.**⁷
 - To write an initial version of the final dissertation.
8. Which punctuation mark should be used to introduce a list?
- Semicolon.

⁵ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 35.

⁶ World Health Organization, *WHO Editorial Style Manual* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 1993), 52.

⁷ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 3.

- Comma.
- Dash.
- Colon.**⁸

9. What is the central characteristic of qualitative data analysis?

- Predicting outcomes through numerical data.
- Theme and pattern analysis and identification in text data.**⁹
- Using random sampling methods.
- In statistical terms, to ensure high external validity.

10. In Chicago style, in what order should citations appear when creating a bibliography?

- In order of publication date.
- Alphabetical by title.
- Grouped by source type.
- Alphabetically by last name.**¹⁰

⁸ Sampson, *A Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 3.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 187.

¹⁰ Turabian, 139.

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